

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Tsivinskaya, A.(2022). University-journal closure: Publication culture in Russian universities. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22192).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6936137>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

#STI22GRX

University-journal closure: Publication culture in Russian universities¹

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Introduction

The organisational culture can have a great impact on the choice of where to publish your research. Caught up in the constant race to publish more papers, some scholars are engaged in questionable research practices (publishing in predatory journals or plagiarising others works), especially if the cash-per-publication reward policy is present (Quan et al. 2017). We analyse the relationship between universities and journals in Russia with the focus on the specific case of organizational university-journal pairing. The intellectual closure between journals and universities creates the echo chamber where the research is published only by one organisation and also read and cited if at all by the same organisation in journal (Subramaniam et al. 2014). This is also the direct and visible consequence of academic inbreeding in Russian Higher education system and its propagating force (Sivak and Yudkevich 2009).

The aim of our analysis is to build a map of institutions and identify groups of universities similar in terms of publication profiles using a two-mode network between universities and journals (García et al. 2012). This research is grounded on the idea that researchers from different institutions prefer to publish their work in a different subset of journals in terms of not only disciplinary mixture but also quality and impact. The relationship between institutions and journals is utilized to identify scientific community clusters employing a co-clustering detection on a bipartite network. Our proposed approach is applied to the Russian universities using the data collected from the national bibliometric database (RISC). We chose this source over other alternatives as it has better coverage of journals compare to international databases which are skewed towards natural sciences and the English language. With our data, we have an opportunity to identify whether universities strive to publish in international journals or oriented towards the production of knowledge only for the local market. We hope that this way we can also show that questionable research practices are not only individual-based decisions but also a reflection of the peer community.

¹ This work was supported by of Russian Science Foundation No 21-1800519

Data and Methods

Our main data source is the Russian Science Citation Index (RISC), which is a national citation database (Moskaleva et al. 2018) with many bibliometric indicators and the Monitoring of Performance of Educational Organizations (Guba et al. 2020). The Monitoring of Performance contains microdata available at the level of individual universities on a census basis about almost the entire population of HEIs in Russia.

Initially, we had sample size=1007 universities that have been registered as an organization in the RSCI. For every university we collected the list of journals where they published. There are 33500 unique titles for observed population of universities collectively. 556 universities have been internal connection such being a founder, on the editorial board or a publishing house at least in one journal. There 2204 out of 33500 that have ties with universities. On average universities that have publishing activities have connection with 4 journals.

For every university in our sample, we would have information about in which journals papers are published, so we can construct a university-journal matrix. This matrix can be used to specify a bipartite bibliometric network where nodes represent universities and journals linked together when someone from a university published in a journal. With our data, we identified the connections between local journals and universities.

Preliminary analysis

In our analysis we would like to show main characteristics of Russian journals established by universities. The “Vestnik” journals represent the most which shows strong organisational ties to their universities as their usually contain the name of the university in the title signaling their closed nature for outsiders. There is 595 Vestnik journals in total in our data set of 2201 university journals.

Table 1. Number of journals by foundation year.

Year	All	Vestnik	Other
Before 1991	305	37 (12.1 %)	268 (87.9 %)
1991-2000	394	156 (39.6 %)	238 (60.4 %)
2001-2010	746	260 (34.9 %)	486 (65.1 %)
2011-2020	720	135 (18.8 %)	585 (81.2 %)

The boom of founding journals by universities started in 90s with the changes in policies and massification of higher education (Table 1). The Vestnik journals have their peak in establishing between 2001-2010 totaling to 43.7 % of existing ones nowadays.

Table 2. Indexing in databases and lists for journals.

Set	All	Vestnik	Other
VAK approved	1210	375 (31.0 %)	835 (69.0 %)
RISC	1939	537 (27.7 %)	1402 (72.3 %)
RISC core	480	94 (19.6 %)	386 (80.4 %)
RSCI	393	83 (21.1 %)	310 (78.9 %)
Scopus	190	30 (15.8 %)	160 (84.2 %)
WoS	134	28 (20.9 %)	106 (79.1 %)

Almost all university journals are presented in RISC (Table 2). 63% of the Vestnik journals are included in the list of VAK approved journals. These publications can be counted towards the requirement for number of publications a PhD candidates and doctors defenses in universities.

Only around 5 % percent of the university journals are indexed in international databases (Scopus and WoS).

Table 3. Representation of language in journals.

Language	All	Vestnik	Other
Russian	2146	595	1551
English	1290	338	952
Other languages	181	42	139

All Vestnik journals publish papers in Russian language (Table 3). More than a half (56.8 %) of them also published papers in English. Less than one percent of journals except papers in any other language.

Table 4. Discipline mix in journals.

Multidisciplinarity	All	Vestnik	Other
Multidisciplinary	112	47 (41.9 %)	65 (58.1 %)
Multidisciplinary in STEM	73	33 (45.2 %)	40 (54.8 %)
Multidisciplinary in SSH	159	54 (34 %)	105 (66 %)
Not Multidisciplinary	1859	461 (24.8 %)	1398 (75.2 %)

The majority of university journals are not multidisciplinary (Table 4). However, 22.5 % of Vestnik journals have some form of multidisciplinary compared to other with only 13.1 %. In general, as Vestnik journals are the outlets to pass publications threshold for the purpose of gaining a degree or for evaluation of personal it corresponds with all disciplines that are represented in the university. Journals for specific disciplines and in SSH tend to have more creative names for their journals.

Table 5. Bibliometric indicators for journals.

	Median			Mean		
	All	Vestnik	Other	All	Vestnik	Other
Number of citations to the most cited paper	4	4	4	11.3	11.3	11.3
Average number of pages per paper	7.6	5.1	7.6	7.8	8.0	7.7
Average number of authors per paper	1.6	1.6	1.6	1.8	1.7	1.8
Average number of citations	13	13	13	14.7	14.2	14.9
Average h-index of authors	5.7	4.9	5.9	5.6	5.4	5.7
Average age of authors	47.7	47.1	47.8	41.5	42.7	41.1
HHI by author organisations	1598	1992	1442	2372.7	2581.9	2295.2

As you can see from the Table 5 Vestnik journal are less diverse in terms of organisations that published papers in them. Over the period from 2011 to 2020 the HHI index didn't show any

trend toward the change for this metric. Other bibliometric indicators do not differ significantly between those groups of journals.

Discussion

In our analysis we would This coupling between universities and journals leads to intellectual closure where scholars are never really exposed to international publishing culture. As the result of this could be strong belief that to publish in English or in international journals is only possible for money. Under “publish or perish” paradigm many resort to choose predatory journals as they do not see the difference between good and practices and merely as a function to pass the criteria for evaluation purposes in their institutions. Papers in universities own journals rite of passage for many students and also viewed as a formality to get a degree. It could be a training ground before choosing to pursue academic publishing however less it is for outsider the lower is the quality standards and the “good” scientific ethos practices are nor being pass to the new generation of researchers.

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